

Applicability of Out-of-Class Education in Gastronomy Education in Turkey¹

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the applicability of out-of-class education in gastronomy education in Turkey. The research was designed based on a phenomenological approach within qualitative research methods. The study group consists of eight administrators involved in organizing such activities. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using content analysis.

The findings revealed several themes related to the definition, advantages, limitations, planning processes, and implementation dimensions of out-of-class gastronomy education. The results indicate that these activities contribute to the development of students' professional skills, enhance the permanence of learning, and provide valuable industry experience. However, factors such as cost, time constraints, organizational challenges, and safety concerns were

identified as key elements limiting the applicability of these practices. In addition, effective planning processes, stakeholder collaboration, and institutional support were found to play a critical role in successful implementation.

This study contributes to the literature by offering a definition of out-of-class gastronomy education and providing conceptual and practical insights into its applicability. The findings are expected to guide educators and practitioners in planning and implementing such educational activities.

Keywords: Culinary Education, Out-of-Class Education, Vocational Education.

JEL Codes: I20, I21, I23

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1. Introduction

One of the biggest obstacles to learning is a lack of motivation for school and coursework (James & Williams, 2017). This lack of motivation stems from students being deprived of interaction in the environments where they receive education (Ertürk, 1998). In contrast, humans are organisms constantly interacting with their environment (Yazıcı & Çobanođlu, 2017). In response to this problem, there has been an increase in initiatives to enhance out-of-class activities that boost students' motivation in courses (Füz, 2018). This allows students to improve both their academic development in that course and their sensory abilities through active activities (Cho et al., 2019).

Philosophers and educational scientists such as Comenius, Rousseau, Pestalozzi, and Dewey laid the foundations for out-of-class education (Smith, 1995). In its modern sense, out-of-class education is considered a new method (Gilbertson et al., 2006). In this context, out-of-class education was accessible in the official programs of Broadoaks Schools in the 19th century. This method was first included in primary education programs in 1912 (Stine, 1997). Out-of-class education was observed to be implemented within the scope of scouting and camping activities in the early 20th century (Sharp, 1943). The "Human and Environment" conference held in 1972 accelerated environmental activities, and the Tbilisi Declaration was published in 1977. This declaration emphasized the necessity of out-of-class educational activities (Yazıcı & Çobanođlu, 2017).

Out-of-classroom education is frequently discussed by educational science researchers today. However, there is limited research on this topic specifically within vocational and gastronomy education. In Turkey, existing studies on gastronomy education mainly focus on issues such as curriculum development (Aslan & Aktaş, 2011; Çalıřkan, 2022; Çarbuđa et al., 2018; Devci et al., 2017; Güdek & Boylu, 2017; Öney 2016; Temizkan & Sever, 2021; Yıldız & Aslan, 2019), practical training (Akođlu et al., 2017; Beyter et al., 2019; Çavuřođlu, 2021; Öney, 2016; Sevim & Görkem, 2015), internship studies (Akın, 2018; Babaç & Önceł, 2018; Beyter et al., 2019; Özer, 2020), the inadequacy of practical education (Akođlu et al., 2017; Aydemir & Buyruk, 2019; Babaç & Önceł, 2018; Beyter et al., 2019; Çavuřođlu, 2021; Öney, 2016; Sevim & Görkem, 2015), and the conceptualization of gastronomy education (Cizreliođulları & Altun, 2019; Özer, 2020; Yılmaz, 2018). Although these studies contribute to understanding different aspects of gastronomy education, research examining teaching methods and techniques that can be applied in gastronomy education remains limited.

Previous studies indicate that out-of-classroom education provides significant educational benefits. For instance, Lee et al. (2025) reported that it increases

academic achievement, provides psychological benefits, creates a sense of belonging, and positively affects student motivation. Dewi et al. (2025) noted that these activities enhanced student participation, strengthened the connection between theory and practice, and improved overall learning outcomes. Similarly, Mann et al. (2022) observed that nature-based out-of-class activities contributed positively to students' personal, academic, and social development. Gastronomy education already includes various out-of-class activities such as on-the-job training, gastronomy workshops, gastronomy tours, gastronomy events, and internships (Sarıođlan et al., 2024). Despite these examples, the applicability of out-of-classroom education as a structured educational approach in gastronomy education has not been sufficiently examined. Therefore, this study aims to determine the applicability of out-of-classroom education in gastronomy education in Turkey and to contribute to the more effective implementation of vocational and gastronomy education.

2. Literature Review

Education refers to activities carried out in a planned or unplanned manner that aim to develop and transform individuals' cognitive, physical, emotional, and social abilities and skills (Akyüz, 2012). In recent years, vocational education has rapidly increased both in importance and prevalence (Nguyen, 2023). Countries that place greater emphasis on vocational education tend to experience higher rates of development (Yörük et al., 2002).

Since the 21st century, the tourism sector has continued to grow steadily. Within this context, there has been an increasing demand for qualified personnel in the sector (Solmaz & Erdođan, 2013). The schools established to provide tourism education aim to meet this demand (Emir et al., 2010). In this regard, gastronomy education has become an important field within educational sciences (Sarıođlan, 2016).

Gastronomy is defined as a discipline that guides individuals on what to eat and drink, where, when, in what manner, and in which combinations (Santich, 2004). Gastronomy tourism has been steadily increasing its economic value within the tourism sector (Dixit, 2019). The foundations of gastronomy education date back to the 17th and 18th centuries in France, where training programs were organized to provide high-quality service to the nobility (Zopiatis et al., 2014). In Turkish culture, the foundations of education in this field are based on the Ahi Organization (Civelek, 2014). After the 2000s, gastronomy education has become a globally popular field of education (Çalıřkan, 2022).

Agyeiwaah et al. (2019) categorize gastronomy tourism into three main types: observational, experiential, and participatory. These activities are also

widely used in out-of-class education practices. Out-of-class learning is carried out through hands-on activities such as lessons outside the classroom, nature and environmental activities (Sari & Paidi, 2018), artistic activities, camps, sports, drama, games, excursions, and observations (Öztürk Aynal, 2013). Considering the definition of out-of-class activities, out-of-class educational activities in gastronomy education include workshops (Boyras et al., 2018), field trips to food and beverage businesses (Seçim, 2020), and on-the-job training activities (artuklu.edu.tr, 2026; erbakan.edu.tr, 2026; Sariođlan et al., 2024; turizm.aku.edu.tr, 2026). Additionally, internships are conducted by both formal and informal institutions providing tourism education, enabling students to develop their practical skills (Lam & Ching, 2007). This allows students to receive training in a real business environment (Dario & Štetić, 2017).

2.1. Out-of-Class Education in Gastronomy Education

Within the scope of this study, out-of-class gastronomy education activities that fit the definition of out-of-class education are discussed under this heading.

2.1.1. On-the-job training

In recent years, some gastronomy and culinary arts departments have included courses such as “Business Education” or “On-the-Job Training,” which involve out-of-class learning activities. These courses are generally offered as electives and may replace several theoretical elective courses. Through this system, students gain practical experience in real work environments for an extended period. Thus, in addition to their theoretical education at school, students have the opportunity to develop professional skills through hands-on training in businesses outside the classroom (artuklu.edu.tr, 2026; erbakan.edu.tr, 2026; Sariođlan et al., 2024; turizm.aku.edu.tr, 2026).

2.1.2. Gastronomy workshops

Workshops refer to groups of people who come together to discuss a specific topic and carry out practical activities. Seminars and training sessions may also be included within this scope (dictionary.cambridge.org, 2026). In gastronomy education, workshops are frequently used to reinforce theoretical knowledge through practice and to develop professional skills. In this context, workshops are organized on topics such as coffee preparation, cake and pastry making, chocolate production, world cuisines, and Far Eastern cuisine. These activities are generally conducted by professional chefs (Boyras et al., 2018).

2.1.3. Gastronomy trips

This method involves planned, scheduled activities outside of school to reinforce the topics students learn in school (Demirel, 2009). Gastronomy trips generally include activities such as participating in local cooking competitions, attending gastronomy-themed festivals, visiting food production facilities, visiting famous restaurants, attending exhibitions of local food and beverages, and tasting (Hall & Mitchell, 2007).

2.1.4. Culinary education organizations

Gastronomy and food festivals, culinary days, and cooking courses are organized in Turkey to support gastronomy education (Sormaz et al., 2020). The Mengen National Cooking Camp is one such event designed for this purpose. This week-long event offers various gastronomy training programs, with participation from students and academics from across Turkey (Kurnaz et al., 2018).

2.1.5. Internships

Internships are programs that allow students to apply theoretical knowledge and gain practical experience in real work environments while developing professional skills. In gastronomy education, internships play a significant role (Akin, 2018), as workplace experiences help students progress toward their career goals (Dolmacı & Duran, 2017). They also benefit workplaces and the industry, partially meeting the sector’s need for qualified personnel through interns from vocational institutions (Tektaş et al., 2016).

As discussed above, many gastronomy education activities can be considered within the scope of out-of-class education. However, studies examining the applicability of these activities in gastronomy education remain limited. Therefore, investigating the applicability of out-of-class education in gastronomy education is important for improving both educational quality and professional competencies.

2.2. Related Research

A number of studies have examined out-of-class education, and selected examples are presented below:

Wang (2024) emphasized the increasing need for out-of-class education activities, particularly as students’ progress to higher educational levels, and explored the correlation between these activities and academic achievement. The study highlighted the importance of activities outside the classroom in developing students’ cognitive and social abilities and provided recommendations for institutions, educators, and students to ensure effective implementation.

Nassar et al. (2025) examined the impact of out-of-class education on students' academic performance, university experience, and institutional reputation. The results indicated that such activities positively influence student success, enhance university experiences, and contribute to the institution's reputation.

Yusupbayevna (2023) focused on primary school students and reported that sports, art, and community service activities enhance cognitive, social, and emotional learning. The study emphasized that structured participation in these activities can improve overall student development.

Muharom et al. (2022) investigated the use of digital devices in out-of-class English education with 267 students and found that these tools significantly enhance learning outcomes and student engagement.

Avacı and Gümüő (2020) conducted a six-week study with control and experimental groups and determined that students participating in out-of-class activities developed a more positive attitude towards social studies compared to those in the control group.

Aslan and Demirciođlu (2019) reported that chemistry students who engaged in out-of-class activities achieved necessary learning outcomes more effectively, highlighting the practical benefits of such approaches.

Ocak and Korkmaz (2018) explored preschool and science teachers' perspectives on out-of-class learning environments. Findings indicated that these activities facilitate learning by doing, promote long-term retention, and support overall student development, although challenges such as crowded classrooms, financial constraints, and safety concerns were noted.

Türkmen (2018) examined middle school teachers' views and found that out-of-classroom environments help link theoretical knowledge to real-life applications. The study also identified limitations, including economic and bureaucratic obstacles and inconsistent implementation across subjects.

Avacı Akçalı (2015) investigated teachers' and prospective teachers' opinions on out-of-class history education. Semi-structured interviews revealed that well-structured activities can enhance understanding, engagement, and teaching effectiveness in history classes.

3. Method

3.1. Purpose of the Research

This study aimed to determine the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey. It also aimed to define out-of-class gastronomy education and identify its limitations and positive aspects.

3.2. Research Method (Model)

Qualitative research is an umbrella term encompassing numerous concepts that cannot be explained in a single sentence (Yıldırım, 1999). The concept of qualitative research can also be expressed as research used to collect qualitative data, such as observation, interview, and document analysis (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008).

This study, conducted to determine the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey, employed phenomenology, a qualitative research method. This method investigates the existence of events and phenomena by seeking answers to the question What is reality? (Baş & Akturan, 2017). In phenomenology, the researcher does not simply take the information obtained through the experiences of the individuals interviewed for the study as it is. In addition, they interpret these statements in depth (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Two approaches are used in phenomenology: descriptive and interpretive (Yalçın, 2022). In descriptive phenomenology, pioneered by Husserl, the aim is to reveal and understand lived experiences. In interpretive phenomenology, the details within experiences are explored and interpreted. The pioneer of this approach is Heidegger (Kıral, 2021). In this study, interpretive phenomenology was employed.

3.3. Qualitative Data Collection Tool

Interviewing individuals involved in a topic or event is one of the most effective ways to examine it in detail, within a cause-and-effect framework (Turnuklu, 2000). Semi-structured interviews are important because they allow the participant to ask a variety of questions, in addition to the questions prepared in advance by the researcher, as the interview progresses (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005).

In this study, interviews, a qualitative data collection method, were used to determine the applicability of out-of-class education in gastronomy education in Turkey. To develop this tool, a semi-structured interview form was created based on a detailed review of the literature. In this context, very limited sources were available regarding out-of-class learning in gastronomy education. The interview questions were developed based on the studies of Torun (2021) and Türkmen (2018). In this context, an eight-question pool was subjected to expert opinion. To ensure scale validity (Yurdugöl, 2005), the opinions of two professors, two associate professors, and one assistant professor were obtained within the scope of the expert opinion. The semi-structured interview form, comprising four main questions and demographic items, was developed based on the research objectives. Following expert review, the draft form

was subjected to a pilot study to assess its clarity and applicability, and it was finalized in line with the feedback obtained. Accordingly, the questions included in the semi-structured interview form are as follows:

- What is Out-of-Class education in gastronomy education? What does it mean to you?
- What contributions can Out-of-Class education activities make to gastronomy education? Should this method be used in gastronomy education? Why?
- Where are the Out-of-Class education environments that can be used in gastronomy education? What activities can be done within the scope of Out-of-Class education in gastronomy education?
- What limitations/problems are encountered when implementing Out-of-Class education activities? How can these problems be solved?

3.4. Study Group

Managers possess numerous competencies to ensure success in their institutions (Bolat et al., 2008) and possess conceptual, analytical, and decision-making skills (Çetinkaya & Özkutlu, 2010). To obtain in-depth information on the subject, the study's population consists of managers of institutions that provide non-formal gastronomy education. Managers were specifically selected because they are actively involved not only in the administrative processes of educational activities but also in the planning, organization, and sometimes the implementation of gastronomy training events. Therefore, they possess comprehensive knowledge regarding the organization, management, and practical execution of out-of-class gastronomy education activities. Face-to-face interviews were conducted with managers of institutions providing non-formal gastronomy education within this population. This allows for a smaller participant group compared to quantitative research. In-depth research is conducted with a predetermined population (Baltacı, 2019).

The sample size for the qualitative study was determined using theoretical sampling. In this context, a sample is not determined in advance, and data collection is terminated at the saturation point, determined by the similarity of the data obtained from the research. This approach does not include a specific target participant logic at the beginning of the study. The data collection process is terminated when the data obtained through the research repeat themselves and reach saturation (West, 2001). In theoretical sampling, the sample is determined incrementally as the research continues (2000, Cutcliffe). In other words, new interviews are conducted based on the analyses conducted after the interviews, and new participants are included in the sample (Baş & Akturan, 2017).

The "Semi-Structured Interview Form on the Applicability of Out-of-class Education in Gastronomy Education in Turkey," developed for the research, was administered to eight individuals selected through theoretical sampling. A total of 24 participants were offered interviews during the process; however, 16 individuals declined to participate and the interviews were conducted with eight volunteer participants. Voluntary participation is also important for the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained in qualitative research (Güler et al., 2015).

During the interview process, the emergence of new codes was monitored continuously. While a high number of new codes emerged in the initial interviews, the number of new codes gradually decreased and no new codes appeared after the sixth interview. The seventh and eighth interviews confirmed this pattern. A total of 55 codes were identified in the study, and the repetition of codes indicated that data saturation had been reached. Therefore, the data collection process was terminated after the eighth interview and the data analysis phase began.

3.5. Research Implementation Process

The semi-structured interview form developed for the research was administered to eight volunteer participants between February 15 and June 15, 2025. The interviews were carried out through a combination of face-to-face and online sessions. Face-to-face interviews were audio-recorded using a mobile phone, whereas online interviews were conducted and recorded using Zoom. The audio recordings of eight participants totalled 3 hours, 31 minutes, and 20 seconds.

3.6. Preparing Qualitative Data for Analysis

Audio recordings from interviews conducted within the scope of qualitative research must first be transcribed and then read repeatedly (Glesne, 2014). A total of 8 pages of summaries and 60 pages of extended notes were taken during the interviews. Afterwards, the relationships among the data are revealed, different variations in the data are examined and legitimized, and the analysis is presented within a logical framework (Engel & Schutt, 2017). The same procedure was applied in the present research. Accordingly, the participants were analyzed by naming them as P1, P2, etc.

3.7. Analysis of Qualitative Data

Categorizing/organizing the data obtained from the research around a specific concept is another step in analyzing qualitative data. The notes taken during this stage are analyzed word by word and paragraph

by paragraph. This process is referred to as coding (Güler et al., 2015). Coding is discussed under two headings: theoretical coding and open coding. These coding methods are also referred to as coding based on predetermined concepts and coding based on concepts obtained from the data (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). In this study, the open coding technique was used. In open coding, the concepts under analysis are defined. These are then identified in detail according to their dimensions and characteristics (Güler et al., 2015). MAXQDA Analytics Pro 2020 was used to code the data set in this study. The data obtained from the analyses are presented in graphs and tables.

3.8. Limitations of the Research

The fact that financial resources, energy, time, and organization are concentrated under the responsibility of a single person during the research process can limit the research's scope (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). This study also has certain limitations, such as the number of researchers and financial constraints. This study was conducted with administrators who plan out-of-class learning activities in gastronomy education. As these participants are directly involved in designing such programs, they provide immediate and valuable insights into the subject.

Table 1. Participant List

No	Participant Code	Professional Experience	Gender	Education	Receiving Out-of-Class Education	Duration (Min:Sec)
1	P1	25 years	Female	Faculty of Education	Taken	20:34
2	P2	26 years	Female	Faculty of Vocational Training	Taken	22:28
3	P3	22 years	Male	Faculty of Education	Taken	31:31
4	P4	18 years	Male	Faculty of Education	Taken	25:23
5	P5	30 years	Male	Graduate Program	Taken	35:10
6	P6	7 years	Male	Gastronomy and Culinary Arts PR	Taken	22:30
7	P7	24 years	Female	Faculty of Education	Taken	22:44
8	P8	28 years	Female	Faculty of Education	Taken	31:00

As part of the study, interviews were conducted with managers of eight volunteer institutions providing non-formal gastronomy education across Turkey. Names and institutional information were kept confidential to allow participants to freely express their opinions

Seven participants had 20 or more years of professional experience, while one participant had 7 years and one had 30 years. This indicates a relatively high average level of professional experience. Participants generally graduated from education faculties, but also received training in gastronomy and culinary arts, vocational training faculties, and a master's degree. This demonstrates that participants have significant experience in education and gastronomy

While including other stakeholders could have broadened the perspective, the current participants offer an important source of information regarding program planning. It should also be noted that these administrators have had only brief experience in practical gastronomy education or are currently serving in managerial roles. Perspectives from instructors or students could have offered alternative viewpoints that differ from those of administrators. Their inclusion might have contributed additional insights that further enrich the interpretation of the findings.

This study was ethically approved by the decision of Balıkesir University Social and Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee dated 29.11.2024 and numbered 2024/11-40 (Document Date and Number: 13.12.2024 - E.458038). The research was conducted in accordance with the relevant board's decision and within the framework of established ethical principles.

4. Findings

This section of the study presents the data obtained regarding the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey. Participants' demographic and professional characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

education. Furthermore, all participants had previously played an active role in organizing, managing, or planning out-of-class educational activities. All of these data demonstrate the study group's qualifications in out-of-class gastronomy education.

4.1. Findings Regarding the Applicability of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education in Turkey

To determine the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey, the opinions of administrators on the subject were examined and discussed under the following headings.

Figure 1. Themes and Codes in MaxMaps Graph

Figure 1 illustrates the study's themes and codes. Thematic analysis identified 9 themes, 2 sub-themes, and 55 codes. Participants mainly discussed the definition, environments, benefits, challenges, and solutions of out-of-class gastronomy education, along with other related experiences.

4.1.1. Definition of out-of-class gastronomy education

The literature review revealed no clear definition of out-of-class gastronomy education. To address this, participants were asked to define it. Participant statements were organized into six key themes, with frequencies presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Data Distribution of Definition of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education

Theme	Definition of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education	
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Professional preparation / experience	3 (37.5%)	"We can describe out-of-class gastronomy education as professional preparation activities. I can also describe it as activities designed to gain experience." P3
Complement to in-class education	7 (87.5%)	"Indoor gastronomy is essential. We learn the foundation of education in the classroom. Education conducted outside the classroom to make it more permanent, broaden students' horizons, add new perspectives, encourage them to think about different things, or capture students' attention is also out-of-class gastronomy education. In other words, it's more like a polishing agent. It's complementary." P1
Applicability to all age groups	3 (37.5%)	"This education can be conducted not only with formal education students but also with adults. It can be small or large. It encompasses everyone." P2

Activities conducted outside the classroom	5 (62.5%)	"In other words, all gastronomy education that takes place outside of school can be considered out-of-class gastronomy education." P7
Effective learning method	1 (12.5%)	"As you know, education is no longer limited to desks and classrooms. One of the best learning methods is providing education outside of the classroom." P1
On-the-job training	7 (87.5%)	"Training that can be provided on-the-job in businesses, cafes, and restaurants, for example." P6 "In other words, I think it's more about doing the job in the kitchen, on-site. This way, students can improve themselves." P1
Analyzed documents 8 (100%)		

Based on the definitions above, this study defined out-of-class gastronomy education. In this context, the following definition emerged for out-of-class gastronomy education: *"It is an effective learning method for on-the-job gastronomy education that complements classroom learning, applies to all age groups, includes all educational activities outside the classroom, and provides professional preparation and practical experience."*

4.1.2. Out-of-class education environments in gastronomy education

Although out-of-class education is common in gastronomy, the literature lacks a clear classification of its environments and types. To address this, interviews identified the out-of-class environments used or potentially used in gastronomy education. Participants' statements focused on 14 topics, whose frequencies are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Data Distribution of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education Environments

Theme	Environments	
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Career Day Events	3 (37.5%)	"We can visit the businesses of people pursuing careers in the field. Career days can be organized. It broadens students' horizons." P1
Exhibitions	3 (37.5%)	"For example, we hold exhibitions and charity bazaars. Trainees also gain many other benefits at these events. This year, we exhibited a variety of our chocolates." P8
Social Responsibility Events	2 (25%)	"In this regard, we can reach others through municipalities or social assistance organizations. For example, we can offer treats to nursing homes. These can be offered to those in financial distress. There can be many social responsibility activities." P4
Real Production Activities	4 (50%)	"In places where mass meals are served, students can also organize activities related to cooking for large groups of people." P5
Gastronomy Fairs/Festivals	3 (37.5%)	"I think fairs are one of the out-of-class activities in gastronomy. We've seen great benefits in this regard. Fairs are very useful. A group of participants we visited before still asks, 'Teacher, when will this happen again?' P2 "So, they've generally turned them into something like this. I give examples of Hatay Cuisine, Elazığ Festivals, Diyarbakır Festivals—the municipality and similar institutions also attach great importance to this." P8
Gastronomy Museums	4 (50%)	"This can be implemented starting at the elementary school level. For example, we took students to a museum. They created a workshop within the museum. They explained the process, and then the masters demonstrated different application techniques to the students. They're a perfect learning environment outside the classroom. First, they provide training and explain the museum's history, then take them on a tour. Then, they take them to the workshop. At the end of the workshop, they give you the products." P7
Home Applications	2 (25%)	"Gastronomic education actually starts in our homes. Home is also a learning environment." P7
National / International Projects	8 (100%)	"Projects conducted in national or international regions are very effective. They conduct week-to-ten-day workshops in kitchens abroad." P1

Cultural Production Events	3 (37.5%)	"Villages have special places that reflect the traditional food of our culture. In other words, students can be provided with opportunities not only to engage in gastronomy education and activities within urban culture, but also to travel to more rural areas, such as villages, and experience the live preparation of traditional dishes. This would be beneficial both for the students and culturally." P5
Production Area / Facility Tour / Observation	8 (100%)	"For example, tours of production facilities would be very useful. There's a flour factory around here. You could go there. There could be a yogurt factory. There's a wine production facility. They also work on hotels and meat." P2
Internship	5 (62.5%)	"I think internships would be appropriate as part of out-of-class learning. Duration is especially important in internships. If they're done for a longer period, not just a week or 10 days, they'll have continuity." P1
Workshop	6 (75%)	"We also hold workshops. We specifically offer workshops for students. The reason we offer these is to teach gastronomic arts, for example." P7
Cooking Competitions	3 (37.5%)	"Organizers hold competitions. They choose the first and second-place winners in these competitions." P8
On-the-Job Training	5 (62.5%)	"You could visit places like food factories and catering companies that serve mass food. Students can take part in production activities there." P5
Analyzed documents 8 (100%)		

As indicated in Table 3, the interviews identified 14 distinct environments for out-of-class gastronomy education. According to participants, the use of these environments is encouraged by national education authorities and provides significant benefits for both students and institutions, which are further discussed under a dedicated heading on the benefits of these activities. Production area/facility tours and national/international projects were highlighted as the most effective for lasting learning, as they allow students to observe and engage directly with the production process, providing experiences substantially different from in-class activities. Additionally, workshops, internships, and other hands-on or community-based activities contribute positively by enabling students to develop technical skills, receive direct guidance from field experts, and broaden their professional, social, and cultural perspectives. Collectively, these diverse environments create a comprehensive learning experience that enhances students' competencies and prepares them for both

practical and theoretical aspects of gastronomy.

4.1.3. Advantages, contributions, and benefits of out-of-class gastronomy education

This section examines participants' views on the advantages of out-of-class gastronomy education. Based on the interviews, these benefits were categorized into two main groups, with student benefits examined under eight headings and institutional benefits under three.

4.1.3.1. Advantages, contributions, and benefits for students

This heading discusses the advantages, contributions, and benefits of out-of-class gastronomy education for students. Frequency values are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Data Distribution of Advantages, Contributions, and Benefits of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education for Students

Advantages, Contributions, and Benefits for Students		
Sub-Theme	f	Example Participant Statement
Knowledge and Culture Development	8 (100%)	"At the very least, their knowledge, manners, and culture will increase, and this knowledge will be further strengthened." P5
Application / Practical Contribution	8 (100%)	"The practical aspects are multiplied. They learn how to use those kitchen tools. In our out-of-class training, they both observed and took notes based on the chef's explanations." P2
Permanent Learning	7 (87.5%)	"Outside the classroom, students learn by doing the activity firsthand. It will remain something they will never forget. Its most important feature is its theoretical permanence. It ensures lasting learning because it is applied." P2
Complementing the In-class	7 (87.5%)	"Both trainings have their place. In-class is essential. We learn the foundation in the classroom. Out-of-class is also necessary to make it more permanent. It's like a complement." P1

Preparation for the Future	7 (87.5%)	"We can describe it as preparing a person for positive or negative situations they may encounter later, through observation." P3
Motivation / Providing Dynamism in Education	7 (87.5%)	"In other words, using the same, monotonous methods and techniques doesn't always develop a person. In other words, it adds dynamism by breaking away from the monotonous classroom curriculum." P7
Social Gains	5 (62.5%)	"A participant leaves in the morning, for example, they've had an argument with their spouse or are angry with their child. They come here, and it's therapy for them. It boosts their self-confidence." P8
Contributions in Terms of CV / References	6 (75%)	"Some of our students who received certified training activities outside of the classroom now have employment opportunities in various places with the certificates they received." P3 "It's beneficial because participants can communicate directly with people in the industry. It helps them develop their network." P2

Analyzed documents 8 (100%)

The findings in Table 4 show that out-of-class gastronomy education supports students' cultural and knowledge development while strengthening their practical skills. Participants indicated that these activities promote permanent learning, reinforce in-class content, and help students prepare for future professional situations. The activities also increase motivation by breaking classroom monotony, offer meaningful social gains, and contribute to students' professional profiles through networking, references, and CV-enhancing opportunities. Overall, the advantages cover cognitive, practical, social, and career-oriented dimensions. In addition, participants emphasized that exposure to authentic learning environments enables students to contextualize theoretical knowledge more effectively. Such experiences also foster a deeper sense of professional identity, helping learners better understand their potential roles within the gastronomy sector.

ing environments enables students to contextualize theoretical knowledge more effectively. Such experiences also foster a deeper sense of professional identity, helping learners better understand their potential roles within the gastronomy sector.

4.1.3.2. Advantages, contributions, and benefits for the institution

This section discusses the advantages, contributions, and benefits of out-of-class gastronomy education for the institution receiving the training. The relevant frequency values are expressed in Table 5.

Table 5. Data Distribution of Advantages, Contributions, and Benefits of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education for the Institution

Sub-Theme Advantages, Contributions, and Benefits for the Institution		
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Development of Institutional-Environmental Relations/Promotion	7 (87.5%)	"So, from the institution's perspective, it has an advantage. It makes the institution visible and demonstrates what it can do. This is an advantage." P7
Contribution of Equipment/Tools, etc.	4 (50%)	"Since our institutions lack detailed and well-equipped equipment, businesses are more comfortable because they are equipped to do so. We can implement professional, industrial applications. During training outside the classroom, they can see tools and equipment that are not available at the institution in the business." P7
Financial Contributions	4 (50%)	"From the institution's perspective, carrying out projects outside the classroom has also contributed significantly. Our institution has contributed equipment, etc., which has contributed nearly 1 million liras." P4

Analyzed documents 8 (100%)

Table 5 shows that out-of-class gastronomy education offers several institutional benefits. Participants emphasized that these activities strengthen the institution's visibility and its relationships with the surrounding environment, contributing positively to institutional promotion. In addition, access to professional equipment and tools in collaborating businesses allows institutions to compensate for

their own infrastructural limitations. Financial contributions obtained through projects further support institutional capacity and create new opportunities for implementing out-of-class activities. Overall, the findings indicate that the institutional advantages extend across promotion, equipment enhancement, and financial support.

4.1.4. Limitations and problems of out-of-class gastronomy education

This section outlines the main limitations and chal-

lenges encountered in the implementation of out-of-class gastronomy education. The themes identified based on participant views are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Data Distribution of Limitations and Problems of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education

Sub-Theme	Limitations and Problems	
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Organizational Problems	8 (100%)	"Getting to the site, transporting materials, and properly managing the planning and coordination can all be problematic." P4
Financial Constraints	8 (100%)	"Financially, it's not much of a problem in non-formal education when adults are involved, but in formal education, students' resources can be insufficient for out-of-classroom education." P4
Official Problems	6 (75%)	"I think the biggest, most important, are the official procedures. Official correspondence and procedures are one of the biggest problems." P2
Unforeseen Problems	6 (75%)	"Staff might be sick that day. They might have an accident. Or transportation. A relative might have passed away. Unforeseen things can happen. Even if we take precautions for foreseeable things, some unforeseen events can occur." P6
Transportation and Accommodation Problems	5 (62.5%)	"These kinds of problems arise with transportation and, if necessary, accommodation. If the trip is to be held in very remote locations, there can be problems there." P5
Problems Related to the Workplace	5 (62.5%)	"The people you want to be with at the workplace may not have the time. The high number of people working in the gastronomy field. They don't spend time on out-of-class activities, which is a major problem. Some don't want their facilities or businesses to be seen, and so on." P2
Occupational Safety and Health Issues	2 (25%)	"There may be security issues during trips. Transportation problems may occur. Accidents can occur. These kinds of problems can occur." P6
Pressure on Students	1 (12.5%)	"Businesses don't want to hire regular staff when there are interns and students receiving on-the-job training. It's more profitable for them financially. Students may be subjected to mobbing by businesses during out-of-class training activities. Because they're not tied to a classroom, their human rights may not be protected." P6
Accessibility	1 (12.5%)	"The lack of courses is a significant problem. New courses should be offered as a government policy." P1
Student-Related Problems	4 (50%)	"Fights and arguments can occur in interpersonal relationships outside of the classroom." P6 "The student will bring materials so we can do the activity. Someone else doesn't. The activity remains." P1
Analyzed documents	8 (100%)	

The findings in Table 6 show that the challenges in implementing out-of-class gastronomy education primarily relate to organizational demands, formal procedures, and operational preparedness. Participants noted that planning requires substantial effort and that formal procedures may both hinder and, at times, facilitate implementation. Practical issues such as transportation, material preparation, and workplace coordination emerge as key obstacles. Concerns regarding safety and student behavior further increase administrators' perceived responsibility. Overall, the results indicate that the feasibility

of out-of-class education largely depends on institutional support and coordination capacity.

4.1.5. Solution proposals for limitations and problems in out-of-class gastronomy education

This section presents the solution proposals regarding the limitations and challenges of out-of-class gastronomy education, and the themes derived from participant views are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Data Distribution of Solution Proposals for Limitations and Problems in Out-of-class Gastronomy Education

Proposals for Limitations and Problems		
Sub-Theme	f	Example Participant Statement
Legal Regulation	4 (50%)	"All these problems could be resolved with legal regulation, if desired." P6
Taking Necessary Security Measures	2 (25%)	"Vehicle must be well-maintained. It must be inspected. It must have insurance, a valid visa, and the vehicle must be free of any damage." P6
Acting, Planned and Official Manner	3 (37.5%)	"For example, if you're planning an event, if you start correspondence the day before, you won't have the chance to make it on time. It's good to have a formal and planned event. You have a good precaution against any potential problems." P4
Positive Approach/ Positive Cooperation from External Institutions	6 (75%)	"Institutions, in particular, need to provide financial support. Both the sector and the Ministry need to provide support." P2
Analyzed documents 8 (100%)		

Out-of-class gastronomy education often depends on coordination with external institutions, making systematic planning and clear communication critical for successful implementation. The findings suggest that many of the challenges encountered during such activities could be alleviated through more supportive and flexible legal frameworks, as well as stronger inter-institutional cooperation. In particular, participants emphasized that adequate financial backing, proactive planning, and reinforced safety measures play key roles in ensuring the effectiveness

and sustainability of out-of-class learning processes.

4.1.6. Applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education

This section examined the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey. Participant responses were categorized and are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Data Distribution of Applicability of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education

Applicability		
Sub-Theme	f	Example Participant Statement
Not Applicable / Should not be Used	0 (0%)	
Applicable / Should be Used	8 (100%)	"Out-of-class education should definitely be used. Even breathing the atmosphere there has a positive impact on students. It makes students more enthusiastic and sparks ideas. I definitely recommend out-of-class education." P6 "It should definitely be used. I won't say 100%, it should be used 500%. I've said it again, yes, it's implemented in practice here too. Of course, the theory is explained first, and then it's implemented in practice. The entire kitchen wasn't wasted; lessons are taught so that practice can be put into practice. Nevertheless, even if you put it into practice here, what is the equivalent in the field? I definitely highly recommend out-of-class education to see this." P4
Analyzed documents 8 (100%)		

Table 8 shows unanimous support for the use of out-of-class gastronomy education. Participants emphasized that real professional environments boost students' enthusiasm, enhance motivation, and help translate theory into practice. This consensus indicates that such activities are both applicable and necessary.

4.1.7. Comparison of in-class and out-of-class gastronomy education

This section compares in-class and out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey. Interviews explored which methods are more effective, and participant opinions were categorized, with frequencies presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Data Distribution of Comparison of In-Class and Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education

Comparison of In-Class and Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education		
Sub-Theme		
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Out-of-Class Education is More Efficient	5 (62.5%)	<p>"In the classroom, that is, to give an example from our own course. We can practice according to the equipment in the classroom. For example, it can be difficult to get a macaroni to stick in a classroom setting. But this wouldn't be difficult in a business or out-of-class setting. Because they do those jobs constantly, their equipment, fixtures, environment, kitchen environment, coolers, shelves—everything is designed accordingly, so there's no problem." P6</p> <p>"In-class education is easier to implement than out-of-class education. However, maintaining student motivation through this approach can be challenging. When out-of-class gastronomy education activities are implemented, students tend to demonstrate more positive and motivated learning behaviors." P4</p> <p>"Changing and adapting educational environments can make a significant difference for learners. For example, awareness of local products can be developed through activities conducted outside the classroom. As a result, students achieve more effective learning outcomes." P5</p>
In-Class Education is More Effective	1 (12.5%)	"In-class education takes up more time than out-of-class education. That's why I think in-class education is more effective." P3
Both are Equally Effective	2 (25%)	"Whether an adult or a child, a person must first acquire theory. In other words, how can one transition from theory—that is, without receiving that training in the classroom—to out-of-class practice outside the classroom? They complement each other. Otherwise, the chain will break." P7
Analyzed documents 8 (100%)		

The findings in Table 9 show that most participants considered out-of-class gastronomy education more effective, largely due to the wider practical opportunities, access to professional environments, and increased student motivation it provides. One participant viewed in-class education as more effective because of the extended instructional time it offers. At the same time, the data highlight that in-class and out-of-class methods complement one another; the theoretical foundation gained in the classroom strengthens the effectiveness of practical work outside the classroom, and using both approaches together leads to a more balanced learning experience. Overall, while out-of-class activities are seen as more

efficient, combining the two methods is considered essential for effective learning.

4.1.8. Comparison of the implementation of out-of-class gastronomy education in formal and non-formal education

This section examined the implementation of out-of-class gastronomy education in formal and non-formal settings in Turkey. Interviews aimed to determine which setting is more effective, and participant opinions were categorized, with frequencies presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Data Distribution of Comparison of the Implementation of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education in Formal and Non-Formal Education

Comparison of Formal and Non-Formal Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education		
Sub-Theme		
Code	f	Example Participant Statement
Equal Effectiveness	3 (37.5%)	"It doesn't matter which has the best resources—formal or non-formal. I think it would benefit everyone. It would be beneficial for both. Both are important. Because both are students in non-formal education and students there. Both can benefit from it." P1
More Effective in Formal Education	1 (12.5%)	"In formal education, students are generally younger, so their vital responsibilities are lower. They don't have responsibilities like running a household or caring for children. Therefore, they are better able to participate in out-of-class activities. Some activities can last several days." P4

More Effective in Non-formal Education	4 (50%)	<p>"Of course, it is more practical in non-formal education. In formal education, the subject matter must be covered thoroughly, and practical applications can only be implemented if there is sufficient time. Furthermore, implementing this with younger students, typically aged 16–18, is generally more challenging in formal education. Therefore, it is more efficient in non-formal educational settings." P2</p> <p>"Out-of-classroom learning is not considered suitable in formal education. In contrast, in non-formal education, participants engage in programs for purposes such as socializing, acquiring knowledge, personal development, and self-realization. Therefore, out-of-classroom gastronomy education represents a more effective and appropriate option within non-formal educational settings." P8</p>
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Analyzed documents 8 (100%)

Participants indicated that out-of-class gastronomy education may be more effective in non-formal settings, where participation is voluntary and learners include both young and adult individuals. Some participants noted that whether the training is formal or non-formal does not significantly influence the benefits obtained. However, one participant emphasized that the structured nature of formal education may, under certain conditions, lead to more favorable outcomes.

4.1.9. Comparison of the effectiveness of out-of-class gastronomy education based on the type of institution

This section examines the effectiveness of out-of-class gastronomy education in different types of institutions in Turkey. Interviews aimed to determine which type of institution is more effective, and participant opinions were categorized, with frequencies presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Data Distribution of Comparison of the Effectiveness of Out-of-Class Gastronomy Education Based on the Type of Institution

Comparison of Effectiveness Based on the Type of Institution		
Sub-Theme	f	Example Participant Statement
More Efficient in Private Institutions	7 (87.5%)	"It would be better in a private institution due to financial reasons." P1 "It can be carried out more easily in a private institution. Because they are not subject to all the rules we are. They can act a little more freely." P4
More Efficient in Public Institutions	1 (12.5%)	"When a budget is allocated for projects, etc., in a public institution, quite large resources can be generated. There is no such power in a private institution. Therefore, it would be better in a public institution." P3

Analyzed documents 8 (100%)

The majority of participants indicated that out-of-class gastronomy education would be more effective in private institutions, primarily due to their financial capacity and the fact that participants are typically adults and volunteers. However, one participant (P3) argued that in certain cases, public institutions may be more effective, emphasizing that project-based budgets in state-run settings can sometimes provide substantial resources.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

As part of the research, administrators of institutions providing non-formal gastronomy education were interviewed to discuss the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education in Turkey. To this end, the definition of out-of-class gastronomy education was primarily focused on.

Given the absence of a clear definition of out-of-class

gastronomy education in the literature, participants were asked to provide one. Based on their responses, a general definition was developed. Accordingly, out-of-class gastronomy education is defined as "A structured, practice-based, and experiential form of gastronomy education conducted outside formal classroom environments that complements theoretical learning, supports professional preparation across all age groups, and serves as an effective approach to integrating theory and practice." This definition aligns with the conceptualizations of out-of-class education proposed by Payne (1985), Ford (1986), Knapp (1996), Dahlgren & Szczepanski (1998). Another issue with out-of-class gastronomy education is the nature of out-of-class learning environments. The literature indicates that out-of-class learning environments typically encompass museums, science centers (Eshach, 2007), nature trips, botanical gardens, science fairs, observatories, anatomy

exhibitions, and parks (Yıldırım, 2020). Kuş (2024) further categorizes these environments into three groups: (a) real-life environments (e.g., workplaces, outdoor settings, and everyday living spaces such as homes); (b) designed learning environments (e.g., museums, libraries, zoos); and (c) school-based out-of-class environments (e.g., school gymnasiums and art studios). While the literature lists activities and environments that fit the definition of out-of-class education, semi-structured interviews were conducted to obtain more comprehensive information on this topic. As a result of the interviews, it was concluded that the out-of-class gastronomy education environments are "Career Day Activities", "Exhibitions", "Social Responsibility Events", "Real Production Activities", "Gastronomy Fairs/Festivals", "Gastronomy Museums", "Home Applications", "National/International Projects", "Cultural Production Events", "Production Area/Facility Tour/Observation", "Internship", "Workshop", "Cooking Competitions" and "On-the-Job Training". The out-of-class gastronomy education environments identified in this study are consistent with those reported in the literature. Furthermore, additional out-of-class environments specific to gastronomy education and vocational training were identified, thereby contributing to the existing body of knowledge.

Out-of-class education is widely recognized as an important component of student development (Christison, 2013), and numerous studies have documented its contributions to various educational outcomes. Previous research has demonstrated that out-of-class education enhances academic achievement (Wang, 2024; Randler et al., 2012), increases interest in courses (Behrendt & Franklin, 2014; Falk & Needham, 2011; Falk et al., 2014), supports motivation (Ramey-Gassert et al., 1994), and improves research, communication, and social skills (Katz et al., 2011; Smith et al., 2010; Sözer & Oral, 2016). It has also been shown to contribute to scientific skills (Bodur, 2015) and long-term retention of learning (Bozdoğan et al., 2015; Guisasola et al., 2005; Guisasola et al., 2009). In addition, its ability to connect theoretical knowledge with real-life experiences makes it particularly valuable in vocational education contexts (Chin, 2004; Erten, 2016).

The findings of the present study are largely consistent with the existing literature, suggesting that the benefits commonly associated with out-of-class education are also applicable to gastronomy education. However, the results also indicate that these benefits take on a more practice-oriented and sector-integrated form within the context of gastronomy education. In particular, the emphasis on practical application, professional readiness, and direct engagement with industry environments highlights the distinctive nature of this field.

Furthermore, the study expands the existing literature by identifying not only student-related outcomes but also institutional-level contributions. While prior studies predominantly focus on student gains, the present findings suggest that out-of-class gastronomy education also contributes to institutional visibility, stakeholder relations, and resource development. These findings indicate that such practices may offer multi-dimensional benefits that extend beyond individual learning outcomes and support the broader educational ecosystem. Furthermore, these findings are consistent with studies examining the impact of educational practices on institutional reputation and external stakeholder perceptions (Nassar et al., 2025). In this regard, the identified benefits appear to function as important motivating factors influencing the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education.

The literature on out-of-class learning highlights several inherent limitations associated with its implementation (Griffin, 2004). In addition to examining the advantages and contributions of out-of-class gastronomy education, this study also considered the structural and operational challenges encountered during its implementation. The findings suggest that the application of this approach may involve organizational, financial, and regulatory constraints. Moreover, issues related to transportation and accommodation, risks stemming from the activity environment, occupational health and safety considerations, student-related pressures, accessibility barriers, and other learner-specific factors may influence the overall process.

In this regard, these challenges may not merely represent technical obstacles but rather systematic issues that require comprehensive planning, institutional support, and regulatory attention. Accordingly, the proposed strategies such as legal regulation, strengthened safety measures, structured and official procedures, and enhanced collaboration with external institutions may contribute to mitigating these limitations and improving the sustainability of out-of-class gastronomy education. Supporting these findings, studies in the literature emphasize that out-of-class education activities should be carefully planned (Bozdoğan, 2012; Bozdoğan, 2018; Ertaş et al., 2011; Yıldırım, 2018).

The study also examined the comparison between in-class and out-of-class gastronomy education. In evaluating the findings, it is important to consider that in-class gastronomy education includes both workshop-based practices and theoretical instruction. Three main opinions emerged within this framework: out-of-class education is more effective, in-class education is more effective, and both are equally effective. The majority of participants indicated that out-of-class gastronomy education is

more effective. However, these evaluations were not limited to the independent implementation of out-of-class education; rather, they emphasized its comparatively greater effectiveness when used as a complementary component alongside in-class instruction. These results support the argument that out-of-class education is most effective when used as a complementary component alongside classroom instruction (Yıldırım, 2020).

Feng (2023) argued that private educational institutions tend to provide more effective education due to their inclusion of out-of-class activities. In line with this perspective, the present study compared the implementation of out-of-class gastronomy education in formal and non-formal education settings. This study concluded that out-of-class gastronomy education can be more effective in non-formal educational institutions. In addition, the effectiveness of out-of-class gastronomy education was examined based on the characteristics of the institutions. Private and public educational institutions were considered in this context. The analysis indicated that out-of-class gastronomy education would be more effective in private educational institutions. Among the results obtained are that the student body and economic situation of private educational institutions are more influential in this outcome.

Following an interview with participants about the applicability of out-of-class gastronomy education, all participants stated that it is feasible and even necessary.

The findings are consistent with Experiential Learning Theory and Vocational Training Theory, which emphasize practice-based learning processes that bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-life experience and support the development of professional competencies (Kolb, 2014; Zaman & Mozammel, 2017). In this context, the prominence of out-of-class activities and real-world learning environments in the findings demonstrates the importance of integrating experiential and vocational approaches in gastronomy education.

These results provide practical guidance for improving the implementation of out-of-class gastronomy education in the fields of education and vocational training. The findings suggest that universities and gastronomy education programs should integrate more structured out-of-class learning activities into their curricula in order to strengthen the connection between theoretical knowledge and practical experience. From an educational policy perspective, the results highlight the importance of developing institutional frameworks that support experiential and practice-based learning environments in vocational education. In addition, the findings indicate that stronger collaboration between educational institutions and the gastronomy sector could enhance the effectiveness of professional preparation by providing students with authentic learning environments.

Furthermore, the study contributes to the conceptualization of out-of-class gastronomy education and offers a structured framework for future research. By clarifying its scope, environments, benefits, and limitations, this study strengthens the theoretical positioning of out-of-class gastronomy education within vocational education literature. Future research could further enrich this field by examining out-of-class gastronomy education from the perspectives of different stakeholders such as educators, students, and industry professionals. Conducting studies with broader participant groups from gastronomy, culinary arts, and related disciplines would further strengthen both the theoretical and practical foundations of this field.

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Applicability of Out-of-Class Education in Gastronomy Education in Turkey

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Applicability of Out-of-Class Education in Gastronomy Education in Turkey

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